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**She VS She:
Are female Mexican engineering students "real women"?**

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ABSTRACT

Women's lack of representation in STEM majors is an ongoing issue in Mexico due to the "Machismo" ideology that predominates its culture. The purpose of this research presented as a qualitative phenomenological study is to answer the following question: What are the stereotypes Mexican female students have against female Mexican engineering students? Our study focuses on 70 Mexican female students that were enrolled in different majors other than engineering pertaining to a northeastern private Mexican university. Their opinions on stereotyping were collected through an 11-question online interview. The first finding was that Mexican female students do hold stereotypes against female engineering students. They vary from levels of intelligence and skill sets, femininity and beauty standards, and lastly, sexual orientations. The second finding was that the transmission of these "Machismo" stereotypes can be traced back to their family upbringing. Overall, these findings contribute to the idea that women's underrepresentation in STEM majors originate before they even start a higher-level education.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Female engineers are a constant reminder of what those willing to transform their lives are capable of; they are able to break the status quo and open a world of possibilities for young girls who want to succeed in any field of study they want. The research conducted by Mexico's National Survey of Occupation and Employment (2018), exhibits a clear imbalance of gender representation on the three more occupied professions related to engineering.

By the end of 2018, the areas of 1) Industrial Engineering, Mechanics, Electronics and Technology, had almost 310,081 professionals occupied, and only 20.6% were women; in 2) Mechanical Engineering and Metallurgy out of the 257,050 professionals occupied, only 9.7% were female; and finally, in 3) Computer science and technology, of the 290,452 thousand only 19.9% were women. Such disciplines are considered "hard sciences" and what several authors classify as STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics).

This gender disparity has been backed up by harsh stereotypes that have impeded women a full autonomy and entailed a deep rooted misogynist and discriminatory logic that, in later years, has even reached the extreme point of femicides. The last one, as reported by the National Citizen Observatory of Femicide (OCNF), aids to the perpetuation of cultural patterns that have been historically assigned to women, such as: "subordination, weakness, feelings, delicacy, femininity, etc., which are rooted in misogynist ideas of man's superiority, discrimination against women and contempt against her and her life" (OCNF, 2018, p. 16).

According to the statistics collected by the Executive Secretariat of the National Public Security System (SESNSP), from 2014 to 2017, a total of 6,297 women were killed in 25 states of the country, from which only 30% of cases were classified as femicides. These figures reflect an increase in the percentage of women killed to be close to 52%, from the years 2014 to 2017. It's not always necessary to talk about the extremes, however, sometimes the worst has to be illustrated in order for the problem to be acknowledged.

Discrimination against women has become so dire that in just three years the rate of murders has doubled. In 2018, the National Survey of Occupation and Employment registered a female economic participation rate of just 43% against a 77% male participation rate. Out of those 43%, merely 14% were female engineers.

In Mexico, women often face discrimination in their work environments. From being forced to take pregnancy tests, being harassed by coworkers in their workplace, or being generally subjected to emotional violence. All this implies that as women are seen as the weaker gender, playing a subordinate role to men, they do not belong in this workforce. With women still trying to fit an ideal gender role, those that do branch out face the issue of a lack of gender cohesion within the work and academic environments.

According to Cortés, Kral & Ramón (2015) an unfriendly environment for women (in engineering) is due to the "masculine engineering culture" and symbolic violence at school and the workplace. For example, male professors' constant usage of chauvinist comments or jokes about women's physical capabilities. It is also mentioned that female teachers and students make the same comments and jokes about themselves. This means that not only the male portion of the equation is the problem, but also the women themselves.

1 MOTIVATION

The purpose of this qualitative study is to identify the stereotypes created by female Mexican university students on female students who study engineering. The study is

relevant due to the pressing matters in society as a whole and engineering career paths specifically.

1.1 Delimitations

Our study focuses on 70 Mexican female students studying fields other than engineering during the Spring semester of 2018, in a northeastern private university.

1.2 Research question

To help us comprehend the magnitude of the problem, the main question is: What are the stereotypes Mexican non-engineering female students hold on female Mexican engineering students?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

It is important to analyze different aspects of women's upbringing, such as their home education, their experiences in school from the first steps up until higher education, and finally their experience during their professional career, in order to trace what originates the problem.

2.1 Women's upbringing and parental expectations

We start off with a disturbing pattern, which is described by authors Corbett and Hill (2015), in a research conducted in the United States of America:

“Despite early similarities between girls and boys in math and science achievement, by high school, boys are more likely than girls to take the standardized exams most closely associated with the fields of engineering and computing. Among first-year college students, women are much less likely than men to say that they intend to major in engineering or computing. This disparity continues into the graduate level. In the workplace the discrepancy persists and, in some cases, worsens, as women leave engineering and computing jobs at higher rates than men do” (Corbett and Hill, 2015, p. 2).

This illustrates the main topic of discussion: from a young age, women are either dropping out of or not even taking part with anything related to engineering for ambiguous reasons.

Taking this into account, the primary source of education, should be scrutinized. According to authors Ginevra, Nota and Ferrari (2015), the influence parents have on their children must never be underestimated. It was discovered that high school and college students' perceptions of parental support had a direct and positive impact on their career interests and career choices, specifically with regard to their opting for majors in information technology.

The answer behind this absence of support is attributed to stereotypes imposed by society. Them being defined as “socially shared beliefs about what qualities can be assigned to individuals based on their membership in the female or male half of the human race...or any other distinction that can be used to divide people into groups” (Lips, 2017, p. 3). Lips also states that:

“An implication of stereotyping two groups as polar opposites is that any movement away from the stereotype of one group is, by definition, a movement toward that of the other group. For instance, a man who acts less rational than the male stereotype is seen not only as less masculine but as more feminine; a woman who acts less emotional than the female stereotype is viewed not only as less feminine but as more masculine” (Lips, 2017, p. 3).

Ergo, women who prefer a more intellectual masculine job are accused of behaving like men.

According to Cheryan, Master and Meltzoff (2015) this is due to the stereotypes engineering carries. These stereotypes can often act as educational gatekeepers, constraining who enters into these fields and driving girls away. The situation they present is related to Computer Science and Engineering. These majors are widely seen as male-oriented fields that involve social isolation, an intense focus on machinery, and inborn brilliance. In the present media, outstanding people that created or are involved with technological advances, are often male figures. Bill Gates and Mark Zuckerberg are some of the most famous examples. In comparison, the scarcity of female famous engineers results in girls having less interest in these fields.

Unconsciously, stereotypes are passed on by generations from a young age, and they can often damage in the future since “we all hold gender biases, shaped by cultural stereotypes in the wider culture, that affect how we evaluate and treat one another. While explicit gender bias—that is, self-reported bias—is declining, implicit or unconscious gender bias remains widespread” (Corbett and Hill; 2015; p. 2).

2.2 Experiences of women in higher education

In high school, girls tend to avoid computer programming classes and any derivative of them, since they are perceived as being “reserved” for boys. In university, this avoidance leads to an ever diminishing female population in engineering majors.

The number of women that abandon STEM majors is distressing but the issue starts with them not even enrolling in these majors to begin with. If they do choose to study engineering, they are at a numerical disadvantage, according to authors Jones, Ruff and Paretti (2013). In university, women almost always comprise a minority in engineering programs. Jones et al. (2013) claim that a thick “engineering culture” prevents women from completely integrate themselves and it is a reason that they prefer to switch majors to one that has a less chauvinistic environment.

Jennifer Hunt (2016) proved that the exit rate for women compared to men is higher from engineering than from other fields, resulting from excess female exits to jobs in another field. She wanted to prove if the considerable literature on women leaving Science and Engineering had to do with the difficulty of balancing long work hours and family.

However, there was no evidence of an impact or influence on having children for women trained as engineers. Rather, she found that the most important driver of female desertion from engineering is due to dissatisfaction over the gender pay gap and less promotion opportunities. This situation is also present in Mexican society.

According to Dharmavarapu & Angolkar (2016, p.1), “women comprise more than 20% of engineering school graduates, yet only 11% are practicing engineering”. As previously stated, a similar percentage (14%) is present in Mexican society, of women actually practicing engineering.

The Mexican university that this study was conducted on has had, since its foundation in the 20th century up to 2018, 111,220 students graduated as Engineers. Only 33% of female students have graduated as Engineers, which includes undergraduates, Bachelor's degrees, Master's degrees and PhDs compared to the 66% of male graduates.

2.3 Female engineers in the work field

In spite of everything, there are women that decide to break from these gender roles and graduate from STEM majors. However, they encounter that the work environment is harder for those that feel that do not belong or that are treated as if they did not belong.

To define this concept of “belonging” in the work field, Wendy Faulkner, in Waltraud & Horwath (2014), analyzed the results of a survey applied to female engineers working in a UK oilfield engineering company. The results indicated that the lack of integration can be easily seen, since men bond through the usage of what are considered masculine conversation topics, with sexual language.

This in turn, makes women feel alienated and in order to fit in, they have to adapt by modifying the way they present themselves. Whereas, some would rather change the way they dressed and acted in order to reduce their femininity; others would rather accentuate their femininity in order to stand out as a novelty. This was also the case in a US software development department.

These two environments created the atmosphere which Faulkner sees as a paradox for women. By making them choose between feeling as not quite “real engineers” nor “real women”. This happens when they either have to exist as the ideal image of a competent engineer which has the consequence of giving up their femininity or being extravagantly feminine and not being considered a real engineer. Women have to reconstruct their identities and potentially give up important parts of themselves or risk becoming ostracized by their work environment.

3 METHODOLOGY

This project is classified as a qualitative phenomenological study, in which an online eleven question interview, was used to collect data (see Annex 1).

The data was a random sample, collected from the 70 responses. It was distributed to the population of non-engineering university female students, through Social Media, mainly Whatsapp and Facebook, and guaranteed their anonymity. The survey was divided into three parts. The first one, basic information about the participant was asked, including age, gender, major and the main reason why they chose to study that major. The second part involved a series of multiple questions regarding their opinions on which major females choose often and which were avoided and why they believed it happened. The last part was an open set of questions, furthering their experience through their studies, asking them to write stereotypes they have encountered or used. The last question asked participants why they believe these kinds of stereotypes exist in society and who passes them on.

We used this methodology in order to analyze the experience that women went through, both as victims and victimizers of stereotypes in STEM majors. The participants ranged from ages 16 to 25 and were currently enrolled in a private, northeastern Mexican university that is often seen for the upper classes. It offers majors of the School of Social Sciences and Government; the School of Humanities and Education; the School of Medicine and Health Sciences, and the School of Business.

The initial codification was to separate psychological and physical stereotypes that students had of the female engineering students. The data was then divided into these new sub categories; the psychological category involved sexual orientation, levels of intelligence and skill sets perceived of women in engineering. For the physical category, answers were further divided into beauty and image standards and social interaction standards.

4 RESULTS

In order for the participants to acknowledge the status female engineering students face, they were asked their general thoughts on the matter. For instance, they were questioned as to which major they thought women choose which one they considered more difficult

and finally why they thought women made such decisions.

As results of the first part of the interview suggests, the participants believed that most women chose to study Business and Administration majors, whereas STEM majors were usually avoided due to the alleged difficulty it presented towards the ideal female gender role. Studying a STEM major would be time consuming for them to perform duties for the family. Thus, women were suited for major pertaining to the School of Humanities and Education as these are perceived as easier and more “people and emotionally” oriented. The second reason had to do with representation, and how comfortable the work environment is for students after graduation. All the participants were aware of the potential discrimination and unequal treatment women receive, such as salaries and preferring men because of maternity leave issues.

For the second part, the participants were asked to think about experiences women go through when choosing engineering as their major. Overall, they said that stereotypes surrounding women studying engineering exist. This made it possible to classify the perceived stereotypes in two categories: psychological and physical. As for the psychological, participants mentioned sexual orientation as the most common stereotype labeling them as tomboys, lesbians and less feminine. A Mexican term that was repeated by 95% of the participants, mentioning that engineering students were “marimacha or machorra (lesbian), masculine”. The low percentage of participation was attributed to the acknowledgement that females had an insufficient level of intelligence and skill set for this field of study. They believe “*women are too delicate and not intelligent enough to study engineering or numbers*”.

The second category regarding physical characteristics was linked to the feminine body and dress claiming that a suit or uniform did not fit the female form as well as a skirt, dress or heels. The consensus defined female engineers as ugly: “*They are less pretty, ugly; the typical nerdy girls: with glasses, badly dressed, and don't care for their image*”.

Finally, participants were asked how they believed these stereotypes are perpetuated. The most common answers had to do with the empirical learning throughout their life, predominantly by female members of their family and professors. They believed it is an innate practice due to the “machista” culture predominant in Mexico.

5 DISCUSSION

After considering the literature review and the results from the online survey, it can be inferred that the main reason behind this social issue is the gender stereotypes of the ideal female role created and imposed by men and females alike.

This ideal image starts being constructed from a young age at the core of their upbringing, the family. Predominantly the female members of the family in a “macho culture” create the idea that women should be delicate and feminine which can often be linked to the idea of gender being self-sacrificing, family oriented and overall, weaker. As girls grow up, their ideals are coerced into fitting a predesigned mold and whoever does not adhere to it, will be criticized and becomes that society's pariah.

Yet, there are few women that do decide to go against the norm and once they prove these stereotypes as farce during their higher education, they encounter a hostile work environment that compels them into adopting new identities in order to fit the standard of “real engineers” which often leads other non-engineering women to deny their status as “real women”. In many instances, these women are victims of the hostile environment caused by chauvinistic comments from both men and women.

Since it ends up being a predominantly male environment, society dictates that it is not a

suitable environment for the gender since it will be harder for females to integrate, *“It is not an environment for good girls”* as some participants mentioned. Cortés et al. (2015) sustained this belief with their own data analysis. Women adapt in order to deal with these hostile environments and they are constantly “navigating between two seas” torn trying to fit into both. This, “by behaving according to the traditional codes of gender (to be quiet, passive), but at the same time exhibit an exceptional intellectual capacity” (Cortés et al., 2015, p. 51).

6 CONCLUSIONS

The initial research question of “What are the stereotypes Mexican female students hold on female Mexican engineering students?” was examined through this study. Even though society strives for diversity and gender inclusion, engineering careers in this type of countries with a patriarchal ideology, seem to fall behind. This study was conducted in order to know what female non-engineering students thought of female engineering students.

Based on the data gathered and the literature review, it can be concluded that most female students acknowledge the existence of stereotypes for female engineering students. These stereotypes are created based on physical and psychological characteristics. As for psychological characteristics, the first characteristic to be identified was the matter of sexual orientation; how women in STEM majors were generalized and said to be attracted to their same gender. The second one, had more to do with levels of intelligence and skill set, and how compared to the male gender, it was inferior. According to the study, females were perceived as less capable, less intelligent and less ambitious, so they are less likely to accept the challenge these presumably difficult major represented.

For the category of physical attributes, the participants agreed that women in this field were perceived as unfeminine and less attractive.

When analyzing the results, it was clear that they recognized how society constructed that the work environment of STEM careers was male oriented and therefore, unsuitable for their gender. This can be a traceable reason why females tend to dismiss anything engineering related as early as elementary education.

The interviews portray a vicious cycle. Due to the lack of female representation, less females enter these fields, because they do not want to feel inferior next to their male coworkers. As a minority, they face gender discrimination by being marginalized, or even overlooked for better job opportunities since they are women. Consequently, less women choose to study anything related to engineering.

Based on the study conducted, the best way to eliminate stereotypes is by attacking the problem from the root. The image of a female engineer should become a more accessible and common image, making the Mexican household acknowledge it as normal, hence, creating the interest for young girls towards STEM majors.

7 LIMITATIONS & FUTURE STUDIES

The limitations of this study included only considering female students enrolled in a private Mexican university and female perspective, dismissing those of males. In future research studies, the perception of male students can be considered in order to know how they perceive these women and how they have experienced certain types of stereotypes within STEM careers. The sample size could also be increased to obtain more precise results.

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ANNEX 1

Welcome message: Hello! This questionnaire is about majors in university, its anonymous and confidential, we appreciate your honesty.

1. Gender? (Multiple choice from Female, Male, Other)
2. Age (Open question for them to reply with a number)
3. Major (Abbreviation of the major they study)
4. Semester (multiple choice from 1 to over 10th)
5. Why did you choose your major? (Three options from “For personal taste”, “Family ideology or pressure” and “Work opportunities”)
6. Which field of study do you think women chose more often? (Multiple choice from Bachelors-Administration, Engineering, Medicine, Architecture, Humanities)
7. Which field of study do you think women find more difficult? (Multiple choice from Bachelors-Administration, Engineering, Medicine, Architecture, Humanities)
8. Why do you think that? (Open question for them to give a long answer)
9. Do you think there are stereotypes for women that study engineering? (Yes or No)
10. Which examples of such stereotypes? (Open question for them to fill it in freely)
11. Who do you think conveys such stereotypes within our mexican society? Explain your answer (Open question for them to answer freely).